

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar and Scheduled Caste Representation

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Introduction -

The most important phase in the movement for social change in the history of India was Abolition of untouchability and human emancipation led by Dr. Ambedkar. His contribution in this movement has been a strengthening of the progressive movement. Dr. Ambedkar's predecessors Mahatma Jyotirao Phule, Savitribai Phule, Gopal Baba Valangkar, social reformer Gopal Ganesh Agarkar, Justice M. G. Ranade made special efforts to eradicate untouchability. Contemporaries of Ambedkar, Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj, Mahatma Gandhi and Vitthal Ramji Shinde, Sant Gadge Maharaj undertook special programs for the eradication of untouchability. Earlier in history, it is seen that not only from Maharashtra but also from India, many saintly traditions have contributed to the eradication of untouchability. Saint Ravidas, Saint Chokhamela, Mahatma Basaveshwar, Saint Tukaram, Saint Kabir, etc., raised a revolt against many undesirable customs and traditions of the society. In the present essay, an attempt has been made to explore the contribution of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar in eradicating untouchability.

History of Caste System -

When the Aryans arrived in India, there was no caste system but a 'varna system' based on occupation. In Arya culture there were three varnas namely Brahmin, Kshatriya and Vaishya. Aryas attacked and defeated the non-Aryans here, enslaved them and created a new caste called Shudra. People who did not follow the rules of the caste system were excluded from the caste system. Separate classes of outcasts arose and these classes were transformed into castes. These classes came to be called 'Atishudra' i.e., 'Untouchables'. The caste system-imposed restrictions on marriage, catering, festivals, religious -cultural events and business. Of course, there are many differences of opinion about the creation of caste system. But it is a fact that the caste system denied social, religious and economic rights to the Shudras and Atishudras here. According to Dr. Ambedkar, "Untouchability is a by-product of the caste system", where the Hindu social system dealt with the Shudra-Atishudras in a very inhuman manner. They were forced to stay out of the villages and do the low-level work of cleaning the filth which disgraces the human dignity. It can be seen that in the 18th century, that is, during the Peshwa period, injustice and atrocities on the untouchables came to an end.

According to Hindu theology, Shudra is the antyaja who appears at the last level in the divine social order. This concept or theory Dr. Ambedkar appears to have refused. According to Dr. Ambedkar, there is no racial difference between upper caste Hindus and untouchables and it has no commercial basis.

Before untouchability came into existence, there was a conflict between nomadic tribes and settled tribes. Nomadic bands were defeated and enslaved

or outcasted. This is how untouchability was born. In return for providing food and shelter, the fixed clan assigned menial tasks to the nomadic clans and the protection of the fixed clans, but kept them outside the village and maintained their outcast status.

After the establishment of Buddhism by Lord Buddha, people of Hindu religion accepted Buddhism. Nomadic tribes also adopted Buddhism. But the Brahmin community spread hatred towards these people and considered them as untouchables. Buddhism declined in later periods, but the nomadic tribes did not abandon Buddhism. Hindus boycotted this community. They were considered untouchables. Hindu social order became stronger. Untouchables began to be treated worse than slaves. The caste hierarchy was based on heterogeneity with the Brahmins at the top and the untouchables or atishudras below the Shudras. Everyone should be given work or responsibility according to their ability or need, but in the Hindu system there is no place for the principles of equal needs, equal work and equal ability. Dr. Ambedkar said that everyone has been forced to do hereditary business in this system, due to which the progress of the society has been stunted and stagnated. Ambedkar believes that a nation cannot be built on the basis of caste because social structure based on inequality will not take the nation forward. For this, a society built on the values of freedom, equality and fraternity will take the human race forward. Dr. Ambedkar asserted that the overall development of every individual should be the ultimate goal of an independent society.

Dr. Ambedkar's efforts for eradication of Untouchability -

Dr. Ambedkar's untouchability eradication work was going on and at the same time the

freedom movement under the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi was gaining momentum in India. Dr. Ambedkar said that he supports the demand of freedom of the country by keeping the rights of untouchables intact. Ambedkar makes it clear. Independence will have no meaning if untouchability remains the same in independent India. Due to the spread of education and the work of social reformers, there will not be much change in the Hindu society. Ambedkar believed that because the socio-economic interests of Hindus were based on the caste system and adherence to untouchability, it was difficult to change the system.

Dr. Ambedkar seems to have suggested some solutions for this he suggested; 'If self-esteem is to be created among the untouchables, there is no option but education'. In 1928, the organization 'Depressed Classes Education Society' was established. Ambedkar believed that education would make the untouchables aware of their slavery and make them ready to organize and fight.

On one side, Dr. Ambedkar seems to be doing Mahad Satyagraha and Kalaram Temple Satyagraha to convert Hindu society and on the other hand he is organizing the untouchables by educating them and preparing them for struggle. Ambedkar seems to have done it not only for untouchability eradication program but also for political organization. Due to political power, the untouchables will get social, economic and educational rights and provide them with means of progress. Ambedkar believes that political power will guarantee individual freedom and help overcome socio-cultural weaknesses. Along with this, Ambedkar suggests that if we want to create a society based on equality and brotherhood for the self-respect of the individual, there is no alternative but conversion. Man is not for religion, religion is for man, so man should be at the center of religion. For this reason, Dr. Ambedkar suggested Buddhism with rationalism and scientific approach to his followers. In Buddhism there is no place for heterogeneity, Chaturvarnya, existence of God, rituals, soul. Buddhism is a religion that believes in democracy and believes in the principle of equality and is necessary for our unity and progress.

After the middle of the 19th century, various social reformers and social organizations took up the task of eradicating untouchability in real sense. The Satyashodhak Samaj founded by Mahatma Phule took up the program for untouchability but in the following period the leaders of this organization could not carry forward this work effectively. Justice Party in Madras and Narayan Guru's untouchability movement in Kerala did effective work. In Maharashtra, Gopalbaba Valangkar Shivram Kamble, Vitthal

Ramji Shinde and Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj worked to eradicate untouchability in the pre-Ambedkar era.

Dr. Ambedkar started the magazine 'Mooknayak' in 1920 after he had studied abroad. He said "In an independent India where the untouchables will not get basic rights, India's independence will be a new slavery for the untouchables," Dr. Ambedkar's public participation in the real untouchability program is prominently seen in the untouchability conference held at Mangaon on March 20, 1920 in the presence of Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj. In this Mangaon Parishad, Ambedkar elaborated on the current situation of untouchables. Education of untouchables, human rights, economic rights, etc. An untouchables council was also held in Nagpur in the same year. The Nagpur conference demanded that the untouchables should get representation in the legislature in proportion to their population.

In the period of July 1920-April 1923, Dr. Ambedkar was studying in abroad. After Ambedkar returned home in 1923, he founded the organization 'Bahishkrit Hitkarini Sabha' on 20 July 1923. Dr. Ambedkar established this organization to carry out the untouchability eradication program more effectively. This organization decided to implement the major program of education dissemination and economic reforms. In 1926, as a representative of the untouchables in the Bombay Provincial Legislature, Dr. Ambedkar and Solunki were appointed by the government.

The Mahar Vatan system, which treats the people of the Mahar caste in Maharashtra, should be stopped. Ambedkar introduced the 'Mahar Bill' in the Bombay Provincial Legislature in 1928. Mahars do extra work, but they get very little pay. He demanded that they should be treated as government servants.

In 1925, Ambabai Mandir Pravesh Satyagraha was started at Amravati under the leadership of Mahadev Meshram. A conference was held under the leadership of Dr. Ambedkar at Amravati on 13 November, 1927 to support this Satyagraha. In the Mumbai Provincial Legislature, Sitaram Bole demanded that untouchables should be allowed in public places. The government also issued such an ordinance in response to this demand.

The *Asprushya Parishad* (Untouchable Conference) was held at Mahad on 19-20 March 1927 in the presence of thousands of people. In this conference Dr. Ambedkar advocated education and economic self-sufficiency of the untouchables. Many resolutions were passed in the Mahad Parishad. Resolutions were passed regarding accommodation of untouchables by upper castes,

intermarriage, disposal of dead animals and eating meat, need of hostels etc. Mahad's Satyagraha created a new consciousness and energy among the untouchables. In 1937, after the court case was over, the ponds of Mahad were opened for untouchables.

In 1929, Parvati Mandir Pravesha Satyagraha at Pune was led by Shivram Janba Kamble and Rajbhoj. The characteristic of this satyagraha was the satyagraha of the untouchables under the leadership of upper caste Hindus. Initially, Dr. Ambedkar who stayed away from this satyagraha, however later supported this satyagraha.

Political representation of untouchables -

The British rulers made some laws for the Indian people. In 1909, Muslims were given political representation. Montague, who visited India in the wake of the Montague Chelmsford Reforms of 1919, met the representatives of the untouchables in India. The British government sent the Southborough Commission to India. Vitthal Ramji Shinde demanded that in the five states (Karnataka, Maharashtra, Sindh, Gujarat and Mumbai) the government should appoint one representative each of the untouchables in the provincial legislatures. Before the Southborough Commission Dr. Ambedkar demanded a separate constituency for the untouchables because no one else could represent them except the untouchables. He demanded that nine representatives should be elected in Bombay Province in proportion to the population of untouchables, one of whom should be elected to the Central Legislature. The Southborough Committee recommended only 7 seats out of 711. But the Government of India rejected this recommendation. Under the Acts of 1919, the Government of India recommended 13 seats for untouchables in the provincial legislatures.

Simon Commission came to India in 1928. On May 29, 1928, Dr. Ambedkar gave a statement to the Simon Commission. In this statement, he demanded 22 seats for untouchables out of 140 seats in the Bombay Provincial Legislature. Instead of direct selection of untouchables, apart from this, Untouchables should be given place in the cabinet. Before the Simon Commission Dr. Ambedkar does not seem to have given much emphasis to the demand for a separate constituency. Instead, he said that the system of joint constituencies with reserved seats should be adopted. The Simon Commission opposed separate constituencies. Out of the total 1191 seats in the Provincial Legislatures, the Commission recommended 71 seats for untouchables, and 12 seats out of the 300 seats in the Central Legislatures.

Dr. Ambedkar and Round Table Conference -

The Round Table Conference was convened by the British Government in England in 1930 to frame a constitution for the Indian people. For the first time in the history of India, untouchables were included in the constitution making process. Dr. Rao Bahadur Srinivasan was also invited along with Ambedkar. Congress had boycotted this conference. In his speech at the Round Table Conference on November 20, 1930, Dr. Ambedkar described the overall miserable condition of the untouchables. Slavery imposed on the untouchables, inhumane treatment, religious boycott, and disproportionate treatment by the British government. Dr. Ambedkar asserted that welfare of untouchables is impossible without political power.

Dr. Ambedkar, Mahatma Gandhi and Poona Pact -

After the first-round table conference, through the mediation of S.M. Joshi and Amritlal Thakkar, On 14 August 1931, it was decided to hold a meeting between Mahatma Gandhi and Dr. Ambedkar. For Congress's demand, this meeting was organized to get the support of Dr. Ambedkar to Nationalist Movement of Indian National Congress. When this meeting was held, Gandhiji told Dr. Ambedkar that the Congress is serious about the untouchables and that the Congress program of untouchables is at the forefront of its programmes. Mahatma Gandhi said that an amount of 20 lakhs had been spent on the program to eradicate untouchability. In this meeting Gandhiji said that untouchables should not be given separate political representation. Overall, it does not appear that much has been achieved from this meeting.

Second round table conference was held in 1931. Mahatma Gandhi participated in the Second Round Table Conference. In this conference, the stand of Congress towards untouchables was explained in detail. In his speech at the conference on 15 September 1931, he claimed to be the representative of the untouchables. But in the second speech, Mahatma Gandhi opposed the political interest of the untouchables. Independent political existence of untouchables will create discontent in the country.

After many discussions, debates and recriminations, Mahatma Gandhi started his fast to death on September 20, 1932 in Pune against the recommendation of a separate constituency. Commenting on this hunger strike, Dr. Ambedkar said that, along with the untouchables, Muslims and Sikhs have also been given separate constituencies, so if Gandhiji thinks that the nation will not be disintegrated, then how will the disintegration of the Hindu society be if the untouchables are given separate constituencies?

Gandhiji's fear is unnecessary. Untouchables do not see any way to progress in Hindu society. In such a situation, political power must be given to untouchables. Finally, Mahatma Gandhi and Dr. Ambedkar and the historic Pune Agreement was concluded. Mahatma Gandhi accepted the demand for more seats for untouchables in the provincial legislatures and the central legislatures.

The British government had given 78 seats to untouchables through separate constituencies in caste elections. Dr. Ambedkar now asked for 197 seats but they agreed to give him 148 seats. The agreement was signed by both parties on 24 September 1932.

Ambedkar felt the need for an inclusive political party for the liberation of the economically exploited and untouchables in the Bahujan society. In 1936 Dr. Ambedkar founded the Independent Labor Party. In 1942, Dr. Ambedkar was appointed as Labor Minister in the Union Cabinet. During this period, he formulated many schemes for the untouchables. World War II started in this period. The political context changed. Dr. Ambedkar dissolved the Labor Party and formed a new party called 'All India Scheduled Caste Federation' in 1942.

Contribution of Dr. Ambedkar in the Constituent Assembly -

The country got independence in 1947. Dr. Ambedkar got an opportunity to work on the Constituent Assembly of India. Dr. Ambedkar framed several laws for untouchables through fundamental rights. Article 17 made practicing untouchability a cognizable offence. Provision was made for reserved seats for untouchables in the central and state legislatures. Article 16 gave powers to the government regarding employment of untouchables. Under Article 46 of the Guidelines, directions were given to make special provision for the educational advancement of untouchables. In this way Dr. Ambedkar devoted his entire life for the untouchables.

Conclusion -

Dr. Ambedkar's work towards the untouchables has contributed so much to the political, social and economic progress of the underprivileged sections of India. Dr. Ambedkar Redressal of Untouchability to Constitutional Rights has a long journey. What little progress is seen today among the backward and disadvantaged sections is only due to Dr. Ambedkar's foresight and vision.

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